

INVESTIGATING REGOLITH PROPERTIES AT LUNAR SWIRLS VIA THE MORPHOLOGY OF SMALL CRATERS. M. Lemelin¹, G. Calas¹, A. Lagneaux^{1,2}, L. Martinez¹, V. T. Bickel³, M. Roy¹, G. Belleau-Magnat¹, F. Diotte¹, and D. Blewett⁴, ¹ Département de géomatique appliquée, Université de Sherbrooke, 2500 Bd de l'Université, Sherbrooke, Québec, J1K 2R1, Canada, Myriam.Lemelin@USherbrooke.ca, ²Géodata Paris, 6-8 Avenue Blaise Pascal, 77420 Champs-sur-Marne, France, ³Center for Space and Habitability, University of Bern, Gesellschaftsstrasse 6, 3012 Bern, Switzerland, ⁴Applied Physics Laboratory, Johns Hopkins University, 11100 Johns Hopkins Rd, Laurel, MD 20723, Unites States.

Introduction: The surface of the Moon is the only body where albedo markings known as “swirls” have been documented [1]. Swirls consist in either single isolated features or large groupings of high and low albedo variations in the form of loops and ribbons [1-3] and can range in size from tens to hundreds of kilometers. Swirls are associated with crustal magnetic “anomalies” where the magnetic field is locally enhanced [1,4,5]. Swirls and magnetic anomalies are both of unknown origin.

Different hypotheses have been proposed to explain the presence of swirls, including the solar wind shielding, the comet coma collision-comet/meteoroid swarm, and the dust levitation/sorting hypotheses. Numerous studies have investigated the spectral and photometric properties of the swirls without reaching a clear consensus regarding their origin but suggest that solar wind shielding and dust levitation/sorting may both play a role [1,6,7]. Few studies have investigated the topography of lunar swirls. Denevi et al. [1] searched for topographic expressions at swirls and found none. Two recent studies, however, suggest that bright on-swirl regions are lower than the darker off-swirl region by ~ 4 m at Reiner Gamma [8] and by $\sim 2-4$ m at the Mare Ingenii swirl [9]. These studies suggest that the topographically low, higher albedo, on-swirl regions support the process of dust migration across the lunar surface, contributing to swirl formation, and argue that on-swirl regions may serve as traps for intermediate-sized (10-1,000 μm) lunar dust grains forming a more compact soil structure compared to the average lunar surface.

In this study, we investigate potential differences in regolith properties between on-swirl and off-swirl regions at Reiner Gamma via the morphologic study of small craters (Fig. 1).

Methodology: We first trained and used a YOLOv5-based model to detect craters across Reiner Gamma in digital terrain models (DTMs) derived from LROC NAC stereo images [10]. These DTMs have a spatial resolution of either 2 meters per pixel (REINER2, REINER3, REINER4), 3 meters per pixel (REINERPHOT2) or 5 meters per pixel (REINER1, REINER5, REINER6, REINER7, REINER8, REINERPHOT), and a relative vertical and horizontal precisions smaller than their spatial resolution. We computed hillshade images from the DTMs and created tiles for training and validation.

The detector uses the hillshades as input and generates a report containing the coordinates of the center of the craters detected as output, along with a size estimate. The model-derived crater identifications are associated with confidence indices that range between 0 (the shape has little chance of representing an actual crater) up to 1 (the shape has a high chance of representing an actual crater). Model evaluation in the test set shows a recall of ~ 0.82 (% of craters found) and a precision of ~ 0.83 (% of identified features correct) at a confidence score of 0.8, as well as an average precision of 0.8.

We developed “MorphoPy”, an automated Python tool, to characterize the morphology of craters. The tool takes as input the list of craters identified by the YOLOv5 algorithm and DTMs to compute crater morphometrics for craters that have a diameter greater than or equal to 20 times the spatial resolution of the input DTM (thus here ≥ 40 to ≥ 100 m depending on the DTM) and 18 complete profiles (1 profile every 10° around the central point). The tool identifies and measures for each crater a serie of metrics: the lowest point, the highest point, the depth (d), the rim height, the apparent diameter (D_A), the circularity, the eccentricity, the rim slope, the wall slope, and the depth to diameter ratio (d/D_A), along with associated uncertainties. We use these metrics to investigate potential differences in regolith properties between on-swirl and off-swirl regions.

Figure 1. The location of NAC DTMs used to investigate crater morphology at Reiner Gamma (solid outline=2 mpp, dashed outline=3 or 5 mpp) overlain by the intensity of the magnetic field [11]. The swirl outline is from [1].

Preliminary results: The YOLOv5 algorithm identified several thousands of craters in each LROC NAC DTM (Table 1). MorphoPy looked through these detections and computed metrics for approximately 30% of these craters. These craters are those that have a diameter greater ≥ 20 times the spatial resolution of the input DTM and 18 complete profiles (no NoData value in the DTM). We then extracted the craters that have a circularity value (c) ≥ 0.8 (to exclude potential secondary craters or overlapping craters) for further analysis.

Table 1. Number of craters detected (YOLOv5) and analyzed (MorphoPy) per DTM.

NAC DTM	YOLOv5	MorphoPy	
		all	$c \geq 0.8$
REINER2	5193	1533	989
REINER3	6159	1670	1093
REINER4	6688	2048	1338
REINERPHOT2	7914	2200	1396
REINER1	5784	3148	1739
REINER5	7916	3347	1994
REINER6	6866	3145	2050
REINER7	6415	3216	2079
REINER8	10039	1587	1034
REINERPHOT	6691	3293	1396

Past studies of d/D values have generally been used to characterize the behavior of fresh craters in different regions across the Moon. Results obtained by [12] suggest that d/D values typically average around 0.2 and decrease with decreasing crater diameter, as small craters may degrade relatively rapidly after formation, a process that would be affected by local topography and coherence of target materials. We tested that general observation on our local measurements and compared the depth versus diameter values for “fresh” craters on-swirl and off-swirl. We defined “fresh” craters as those having a circularity value ≥ 0.8 and a distinct rim in the profiles extracted from the NAC DTMs. These craters likely correspond to crater classes A, AB, and B in [12]. Figure 2 shows the depth versus diameter values for fresh craters located in DTMs at 2 mpp (top) and in DTMs at 5 mpp (bottom). In DTMs at 2 mpp, the depth and diameter values are mostly centered around $d/D=0.10$. The trend for craters located off-swirl (dotted blue curve) shows the decrease in d/D value with decreasing crater diameter as reported by [12]. However, the trend for craters located on-swirl (dotted green curve) does not and rather suggests a somewhat stable $d/D \sim 0.10$ for all crater sizes (~ 40 -1000 m). Both trends start to deviate at $D \sim 100$ m. In DTMs at 5 mpp, the depth and diameter values are also mostly centered around $d/D=0.10$. In this case, the trend for craters located off-swirl (dotted blue curve) and on-swirl (dotted green curve) show the

decrease in d/D value with decreasing crater diameter, although the decrease is more pronounced for craters located off-swirl.

Figure 2. Depth versus diameter values for “fresh” craters at Reiner Gamma located in DTMs at 2 mpp (top) and in DTMs at 5 mpp (bottom) with $c \geq 0.9$. Blue points represent craters off-swirl, green points represent craters on-swirl. The lines show $d/D=0.20$ (solid), $d/D=0.10$ (dashed), $d/D=0.05$ (dotted).

Conclusion: Our preliminary results suggest that the decrease in d/D values with decreasing crater diameter is less pronounced for craters located on-swirl than craters located off-swirl. This may imply a different degradation rate (slower on-swirl) or different target properties (impact into a deposit with more cohesion and strength). We do not see a clear offset in d/D values on-swirl versus off-swirl that would support the hypothesis of dust migration towards on-swirl areas.

References: [1] Denevi, B. W. et al. (2016) *Icarus*, 273, 53-67. [2] Schultz & Srnka (1980) *LPSC XI*, #1360. [3] Blewett et al. (2011) *JGR*, 116, E2. [4] Hood et al. (1979) *Science*, 204, 4388, 53-57. [5] Hood and Schubert (1980) *Science*, 208, 4439, 49-51. [6] Chrbolková et al. (2019) *Icarus*, 333, 516-527. [7] Kinczyk et al. (2025) *PSJ*, 6, 57. [8] Weirich J. R. et al. (2023) *PSJ*, 4, 212. [9] Domingue D. et al. (2022) *GRL*, 49, 6, e2021GL095285. [10] Henriksen M. R. et al. (2017) *Icarus*, 28, 122-137. [11] Ravat, D., et al. (2020) *JGR*, 125, 7, e2019JE006187. [12] Stopar, J., et al. (2017) *Icarus*, 298, 34-48.